

PID Alliance Problem Statement

Background

In recent years persistent identifiers have become widely accepted as a key component of global open research infrastructure. However, their adoption is not internationally universal, and the barriers to universal adoption are not yet fully understood. Transnational PID initiatives such as the European Commission funded [THOR](#) and [FREYA](#) projects have increased understanding, adoption and interoperability of PIDs within a European context, but further work is required to distribute the outcomes and embed them for the benefit of all.

Problem

A 2020 [scoping study](#) of the need for a coordinated community supporting PIDs adoption and awareness, a PID Alliance, found that stakeholders who have not been able to participate in existing PID community mechanisms so far (e.g. membership organisations, working groups or events like PIDapalooza) want to be heard and help to shape the future of the PID network. This precursor study found that adoption of PIDs had been slow due to fragmentary communication of their value and both technical and financial barriers. The 2020 study was limited in scope but identified a key larger issue, and moving forward, a multiplicity of voices are needed to ensure that solutions and best practices are built on evidence of need, not assumptions. While adoption issues still exist in Europe, North America and Oceania, we believe that a focus on other regions is novel and will shed new light.

Known status and regional challenges to further the implementation/adoption of PIDs in Latin-America, Africa and Asia.

- ORCID is relatively widely known and used in Africa – numbers can be partially obtained
- In South America, ORCID is widely known and increasingly used (numbers are available), and Crossref's DOIs are part of several publishing and indexing mandates, so systematically used by university and small presses.

Aims

The overall aims of the proposed work are:

- To gain as full and complete an understanding of historically underrepresented regional areas within the PID community as possible
- To build consensus on the best approach to increase the inclusivity of the PID community
- To influence key stakeholders in the sector to improve inclusivity and communication across the PID sector

It was clear from the scoping study that the PID Alliance could take many forms but it would be premature to determine that before the need had been more rigorously established.

Objectives

As a neutral global initiative, including voluntary representatives from a range of international organisations, we are proposing to facilitate a full and open consultation exercise.

We propose this consultation involve conducting a large number of in-depth interviews (20-30) and a survey of stakeholders from across South America, Africa and Asia (areas historically under-represented amongst the PID community) to gather their views, identify needs and barriers to participation in PID infrastructure to update and inform a revised report incorporating this work alongside the earlier information gathered already.

It will conclude with an international round table event that will bring together stakeholders from all regions to build shared understanding and consensus, and to facilitate networking and relationship building.

Contributing organisations and individuals

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